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3 1 **Regional impacts of global climate change: A local humid phase in central Iberia in a late**
4 **Miocene drying world**

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1
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3 30 **Abstract**

4 31 The end of the Miocene was an eventful period of changes in climate and geography, and a
5 32 restructuring of terrestrial plant and mammals. The tendency towards global aridification has
6 33 attracted much recent interest, and makes the late Miocene a striking case-study for testing
7 34 current and near-future scenarios involving global warming. Little is known however about the
8 35 consequences of these global changes in temperature and precipitation at regional or local
9 36 scales. Given its geographical position and extraordinary fossil record, the Iberian Peninsula
10 37 offers many insights into short- and long-term shifts in climate and their local response. Here,
11 38 we explore the diet and ecology of large-mammals through tooth-wear patterns and examine
12 39 changes in local climate and habitat conditions in central Spain in a period (9.1-6.3 Ma) for
13 40 which there exists a dearth of palaeoenvironmental information. Relatively dry climates and
14 41 open-woodland landscapes evolved locally during the late Vallesian and early Turolian (9.0-7.7
15 42 Ma). Unexpectedly, we detect a period of high precipitation and a peak of humidity at the end of
16 43 the Turolian (7.0 Ma) that prompted the development of wetter, more forested habitats,
17 44 suggesting that the traditional view of the late Miocene as a steppe landscape is a
18 45 misconception. Finally we find a period of relatively drier and warmer conditions from the early
19 46 Ventian onwards. Overall, our finding that a local episode of increased humidity in central
20 47 Spain was synchronous with a global warming trend in Europe evidences that the greatest
21 48 climatic changes may have an opposite impact at regional and local scales.

22 49
23 50 **Key words:** late Miocene, Alfambra-Teruel Basin, climate, mammals, palaeodiet, tooth wear.
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3 58 The end of the Miocene (~9.0-5.0 Ma) was an eventful time with severe geological events,
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5 59 and changing global climate (Zachos *et al.* 2008) and terrestrial vegetation (Singh 1988). From
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7 60 9.5 Ma onwards, Europe was affected by global cooling and increased aridification (van Dam
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9 61 2006; Jiménez-Moreno *et al.* 2010). One important phase in the circum-Mediterranean area was
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11 62 the Vallesian Crisis (ca. 9.6 Ma), in which fruit-rich evergreen (subtropical) forests were
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13 63 replaced by more deciduous, drier forests as a consequence of increased seasonality (Agustí *et*
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15 64 *al.* 2003; van Dam 2006). Due to changing climate and palaeogeography (including sea-level
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17 65 drops and terrestrial bridges), Europe—and specially the circum-Mediterranean area—
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19 66 experienced besides several major biotic events, such as the disappearance of most of the
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21 67 middle Miocene forest-adapted mammals (e.g., hominoids and other humid-adapted taxa) and
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23 68 the arrival of immigrants from the peri-Mediterranean region and Asia (ca. 9.0-7.5 Ma) (Koufos
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25 69 *et al.* 2005). A differentiate (zonal) climate in Spain (Favre *et al.* 2007; Jiménez-Moreno *et al.*
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27 70 2010) was one of the main causes for which many of these above mentioned shifts were most
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29 71 pronounced in inner Spain. All this global tendency was indeed most pronounced in the
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31 72 Turolian (ca. 8.7-7.0 Ma), as denoted by the occurrence of prairies and steppe and subtropical-
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33 73 adapted vegetation (Barrón *et al.* 2010). The composition of the terrestrial mammalian faunas
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35 74 suggests that an important change occurred during the Turolian/Ventian transition (ca. 7.8-6.3
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37 75 Ma) (Morales *et al.* 2013) and that, at ca. 6.1 Ma, an ephemeral landbridge allowed the first
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39 76 exchange between Africa and Europe across Spain (Garcés *et al.* 1998). Finally, a new shift in
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41 77 climate towards increasing continentality and aridity around 5.9 Ma (combined with tectonic
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43 78 convergence between Africa and Europe and the resulting uplift of the Spanish and NW African
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45 79 mountain chains) led to the closure of the Iberian and Rifian Seaways and the complete isolation
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47 80 of the Mediterranean Basin (Krijgsman *et al.* 1999; Morales *et al.* 2013), which culminated in a
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49 81 temporal desiccation of the Mediterranean Sea.

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51 82 Hence, it is evident that the late Miocene has coincided in Europe with the interplay of
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53 83 tectonics and global climate fluctuations—mostly including continentality and drying—which
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55 84 have played a critical role in major biome distribution, the evolution of terrestrial ecosystems,
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57 85 and the emergence and dispersal of new mammalian species.

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3 86 Over the last two decades, considerable effort has been placed on understanding how
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5 87 European climatic shifts impacted the environments and species during the late Miocene.
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7 88 Intense palaeontological (Alberdi *et al.* 1997; Azanza *et al.* 2000; 2004; Fortelius *et al.* 2006,
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9 89 2014; Böhme *et al.* 2008, 2011; Barrón *et al.* 2010; Eronen *et al.* 2010; Jiménez-Moreno *et al.*
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11 90 2010; Costeur *et al.* 2013; Maridet *et al.* 2013; Casas-Gallego *et al.* 2015; Madern & Hoek
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13 91 Ostende 2015), sedimentological (Garcés *et al.* 1998; Krijgsman *et al.* 1999) and geochemical
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15 92 (Domingo *et al.* 2013; Rey *et al.*, 2013) work has positively contributed to this target. So far,
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17 93 however, one of the main problems affecting many studies focused on the late Miocene is an
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19 94 insufficient stratigraphic resolution and the wealth of information available, as they often
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21 95 involve a disparate nature (and uneven distribution) of the awkward information (see Fortelius
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23 96 *et al.* 2006). Maybe this is the reason for which many results conflict. Although some of this
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25 97 dispute may be due in large part to climatic zonation within Europe, with Central Europe
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27 98 becoming dryer and southwest Europe staying wetter—though this is only true for punctual time
28
29 99 intervals and specific geographic areas—the regional effects of the climate of the latest Miocene
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31 100 are still not sufficiently well-known. Also importantly, we still know very little about the
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33 101 palaeoenvironmental circumstances of some of the inner regions of Spain (as the Teruel-
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35 102 Alfambra Basin) during the interval that comprises from 9.0 to 6.5 Ma, since there exists a large
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37 103 amount of proxy data in the literature for these areas, but it belongs to older (early Tortonian) or
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39 104 younger (late Messinian) time intervals.

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41 105 Given a key geographical position of the Iberian Peninsula during the late Miocene—
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43 106 between Africa and Eurasia and between Mediterranean and temperate climates (Jiménez-
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45 107 Moreno *et al.* 2010)—and its outstanding record of large mammals from different renowned
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47 108 localities with well-documented ages (Álvarez-Sierra *et al.* 2003), this region offers many
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49 109 insights for gaining more learning about the short- and long-term shifts in climate during the
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51 110 late Miocene and their regional and local effects. With this aim, we focus on the diets and
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53 111 ecology of large plant-eating mammals from the Alfambra-Teruel Basin (one the best-sampled
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55 112 parts of the late Miocene Iberian record) to reconstruct changes in the habitats in a time (from
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3 113 nearly 9 to 6 Ma) of global climate variations that was of extraordinary relevance for the origin
4 114 of many present-day mammals and the evolution of modern Europe.

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7 116 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

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10 118 *Dataset*

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15 120 The material consists of 483 teeth of cervids ($N = 165$) and bovids ($N = 318$) from the late
16 121 Miocene basin of Alfambra-Teruel (central Spain) (Fig. 1). The sample belongs to 10 different
17 122 localities and spans 4 European Land Mammal Neogene (MN) ages and zonation (MN10-
18 123 MN13, local zones J3 to M2) (Table 1) located in the middle area of the basin, where the
19 124 composite section comprises over 200 meters of late Miocene to early Pliocene sediments
20 125 (Alcala *et al.* 2000; van Dam *et al.* 2001). Most of the sites selected for this study are classical
21 126 (La Roma 2, Puente Minero, Los Mansuetos, Concul-Cerro de la Garita, Valdecebro 3, El
22 127 Arquillo 1, Las Casiones, Milagros; see details in Alcalá 1994), while some others are new
23 128 (Rambla de Rio Seco E and Rambla de Rio Seco K; see Azanza *et al.* 2014 and Pérez-García *et*
24 129 *al.* 2013). Here we use the last chronology for the end of the Miocene according to Morales *et*
25 130 *al.* (2013) in which a new mammalian age named as Ventian is validated. It comprises faunas
26 131 recorded between 7 to 5 Ma, correlatable with the Messinian and divided into zone M (with
27 132 three subzones; van Dam *et al.* 2001) and N (with N1 and N2 subdivisions, Morales *et al.*
28 133 2013). Accordingly, the Turolian is restricted to zones K and L. The specimens are housed at
29 134 the Fundación Conjunto Paleontológico de Teruel-Dinópolis (Teruel, Spain), Museo de
30 135 Ciencias Naturales de la Universidad de Zaragoza (Zaragoza, Spain) and Museo Nacional de
31 136 Ciencias Naturales-CSIC (Madrid, Spain).

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50 138 *Dental mesowear and microwear*

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54 140 There are different dental ecomorphological variables for reconstructing past climate and
55 141 environments based on large (especially herbivorous) mammals. Among them, patterns of

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3 142 dental wear and tooth crown height (or hypsodonty) are the most widely used in the literature
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5 143 (DeMiguel *et al.* 2008). Both variables provide a proxy for the mechanical properties of the
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7 144 foods eaten, which gives clues about climatic data (such as precipitation) and vegetation.
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9 145 Hypsodonty is simpler to compute than dental wear, and it is also quite reliable if used at the
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11 146 global scale. However, it is also much more problematic when used at regional and local scales
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13 147 because the link between dental crown height and habitat type is still unclear. The reason is that
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15 148 hypsodonty is more complex than one might expect, and there are many things to consider, such
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17 149 as allometry and phylogeny, which precludes interpretations of habitat type and environmental
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19 150 conditions (Damuth & Janis 2011; DeMiguel *et al.* 2015). Apart from this, other proxies have a
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21 151 stronger statistical correlation to estimate precipitation values and climatic data than hypsodonty
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23 152 and other ecomorphological variables (such as body mass and body length) (Eronen *et al.*
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25 153 2010a,b). Accordingly, and because *i*) tooth wear proxies such as mesowear and microwear are
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27 154 not related to phylogeny, *ii*) are more effective and informative at the scale level of this study,
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29 155 and *iii*) may capture much of the environmental signal, they are used in this work as a proxy for
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31 156 palaeoclimatic and palaeoenvironmental reconstruction .

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33 157 The tooth-based mesowear method (Fortelius & Solounias 2000)—one of the most powerful
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35 158 tools for documenting dietary abrasion—was used. Upper and lower molars were analysed
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37 159 following Kaiser & Solounias (2003) and DeMiguel *et al.* (2010, 2012). Individual molar cusp
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39 160 shape (CS) and occlusal relief (OR) was computed and then converted into a single mesowear
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41 161 score (MS) for each species following Rivals *et al.* (2009). The comparative extant database by
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43 162 Fortelius & Solounias (2000) of 45 extant ungulates was used for comparative purposes.
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45 163 Additionally, analyses of the microscopic marks (or tooth microwear) left by the foods of the
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47 164 last meals (days, weeks) consumed before an individual's death were performed for specific
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49 165 samples to reconstruct short-term variations in diet and detect seasonality. In selecting
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51 166 specimens, preference was given to second molars (Solounias *et al.* 2000). Given recent results
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53 167 by Ramdarshan *et al.* (2017), we ~~examine-perform~~ microwear using three options for tooth type
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55 168 (i.e., combination of upper and lower molars, only lower molars, and only upper molars) ([Table](#)
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57 169 [2](#)) and see that much of our data are not sensitive to tooth type and that the fact of grouping

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3 170 upper + lower teeth does not inflate the guild of mixed feeder species (contrarily to that
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5 171 observed by Ramdarshan et al. 2017). Because Ramdarshan et al. (2017) based their analyses on
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7 172 microwear texture, a possible explanation ~~for this probably relates to methodological~~
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9 173 ~~differences. Thus, it~~ may be ~~possible~~ that traditional microwear variables (scratches and pits)
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11 174 ~~would bear~~ more robust than texture variables (complexity, anisotropy, heterogeneity, etc) and
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13 175 do not show so much dependence on the type of tooth (upper versus lower) selected for study.

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15 176 ~~Accordingly, here we performed microwear using the combination of upper and lower molars,~~
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17 177 ~~as it is customarily common in microwear research and allows for the largest sample size.~~

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19 178 Micrographs of occlusal enamel surfaces were taken at 500x with an ESEM, and microscopic
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21 179 wear traces (pits and scratches) analysed using Microware 4.02[©] software (kindly provided by
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23 180 P. Ungar) in a 0.4 mm square area. The number of scratches and pits were transformed into a
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25 181 density score in order to simplify the comparison of fossils with other taxa. A set of 28 extant
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27 182 ungulates with well-known diets derived from Solounias *et al.* (2000) was used for comparison.

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30 184 *Statistical tests*

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34 186 Hierarchical, complete-linkage (Ward's method) cluster analyses based on Euclidean
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36 187 distances and discriminant Canonical Variate Analyses were carried out to characterise dietary
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38 188 traits of species. The combination of rounded and blunt cusps, and high relief were used for the
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40 189 mesowear analyses as criterion variables. Two dietary classifications, conservative and radical,
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42 190 were used alternately in the discriminant mesowear as a grouping variable. Statistical results
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44 191 (mean, standard error and standard deviation) of mesowear values are also provided for
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46 192 statistical demonstration of the analyses (Table 32). The microwear tests were developed using
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48 193 densities of scratches and pits as variables. Descriptive and inferential statistics were computed
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50 194 using SPSS Statistics 19 software. A more comprehensive description of the statistical
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52 195 techniques is available in DeMiguel *et al.* (2012).

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55
56 197 **RESULTS**

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199 *Tooth wear patterns by time intervals*

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201 *Vallesian (MN10, local zone J)*. Overall, the predominant mesowear pattern is a predominance
202 of high relief and rounded cusps, as well a considerable proportion of sharp cusps. It is also
203 worth noting the incidence of low relief and some blunt cusps in the bovid *Tragoportax gaudry*
204 from La Roma 2 (Table 1). On average, vallesian bovids have a MS of 0.82, similar to that of
205 some extant ruminants showing a highly abrasion-dominated wear though they are mixed
206 feeders. Dental microwear data show a moderately high scratching and intermediate pitting
207 incidences (Table 2) (close to some extant seasonal mixed feeders), thereby corroborating
208 observations from long-term patterns of mesowear.

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210 *Turolian (MN11, local zone K)*. Species exhibit mesowear comprised of a predominance of
211 round cusps and high relief and scores from 0.60 to 0.80 (Table 1) similar to those of extant
212 mixed feeders. Overall, the average MS value for bovids and cervids is 0.68 and 0.80,

213 respectively, which are very similar to those of Vallesian species. Microwear data (Table 2)
214 indicate that *Tragoportax gaudry* apparently depended more on grasses, denoted by an
215 intensively striated enamel surface and intermediate pitting. It thus shares strong affinities with
216 extant seasonal mixed feeders with a seasonal preference for grass. The bovid *Boselaphini* indet.
217 1 and the cervid *Lucentia* aff. *pierensis* from this stage differ quite strongly from other previous
218 and contemporaneous taxa by having lower striation and pit densities (Table 2), a signal also
219 seen in some extant fruit-browsers. Such a discrepancy in the type of dental wear indicates that
220 these two species ate a significant proportion of ligneous, soft foods just before death, despite
221 having a long-term signal more typical of an intermediate-abrasive, mixed feeder. This
222 heterogeneity concerning methodologies indicates a difference between their average trophic
223 practices and of the last meals consumed.

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3 225 *Turolian* (MN12, local zone L). There is a considerable variation in the proportion of rounded
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5 226 and sharp cusps among species, and two trends are observed within this stage (Table 1). On one
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7 227 hand, most of the fossils from Los Mansuetos and Concud (with the exception of *Gazella*
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9 228 *deperdita*) have a combination of sharp and rounded cusps and high relief, and scores between
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11 229 0.56 and 0.66, equalling those of many extant mixed feeders; on the other hand, species from
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13 230 Rambla de Río Seco E and *Gazella deperdita* from Concud have higher proportions of sharp
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15 231 cusps and lower scores that range from 0 to 0.36 (similar to that of many extant leaf-eaters),
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17 232 which essentially suggests less abrasives and committed browsing. Although the restricted
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19 233 sample of Rambla de Río Seco E allows us to tentatively propose that *Hispanodorcas* and the
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21 234 Boselaphini were truly committed to browsing, results for the gazelle from Concud are
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23 235 conclusive, as it comprises one of the largest samples of the study. Overall, there is, therefore,
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25 236 more variation in the diet of MN12 (zone L) species (including foods with less dental abrasion)
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27 237 if compared with MN10 (zone J3) and MN11 (zone K) taxa. This is confirmed by the average
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29 238 mesowear values of this time span (0.37 for bovids and 0.61 for cervids). Dental microwear
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31 239 ([Table 2](#)) for *Tragoportax gaudry* and *Gazella deperdita* from Concud show intensively striated
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33 240 enamel surfaces and intermediate pitting for the former, and a moderately high scratching and
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35 241 high pitting incidences for the gazelle. The high pit densities found in *Gazella* suggest high
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37 242 proportions of woody ligneous material consumed during browsing, which is in full agreement
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39 243 with the browser style inferred from tooth mesowear.
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43 245 *Ventian* (MN13, local zones M1 and M2). We find a great dietary heterogeneity and a wide
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45 246 spectrum of food abrasion for the first half of the Ventian (zone M1) (Table 1). Despite an
46
47 247 extraordinary taxonomic diversity, with at least eight ruminant species being recorded in only
48
49 248 two sites, the number of specimens from this time span is not sufficiently abundant. *Pliocervus*
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51 249 *cf. turolensis* and *Tragoportax* sp. from Rambla de Río Seco K display mesowear mostly
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53 250 comprised of sharp cusps and high relief and scores of 0 and 0.2 that suggest low levels of
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55 251 abrasion, as typical of leaf browsers. *Pliocervus cf. turolensis* from Valdecebro 3 has 50%
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57 252 sharp and 50% rounded cusps and high relief, and a score of 0.50; a signal that reveals that diet

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3 253 was moderately abrasive (similar to extant mixed feeders). Boselaphini bovids from Valdecebro
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5 254 3 and cf. *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* from Rambla de Río Seco K show instead stronger rounding
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7 255 and high relief (though also display significant proportions of sharp cusps), giving an overall
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9 256 score that ranges from 0.60 to 0.80. When compared to extant species, their mesowear share
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11 257 affinities with extant mixed feeders. Finally, *Tragoportax gaudryi* and cf. *Pliocervus* aff.
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13 258 *matheroni* from Valdecebro 3 have more rounded apices and scores of 1.0 and 1.28, thus
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15 259 pointing to higher levels of abrasion in their diets, as typical of grass-dominated feeders.
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17 260 Despite the scarcity of specimens, some individuals of cf. *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* show
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19 261 extensive incidence of blunt cusps and low relief, which is unusual even for the largest samples
20
21 262 here studied (Table 1). This might indicate that this cervid was somewhat more committed to
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23 263 grazing and to the ingestion of abrasives than the remaining. When the taxonomic groups are
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25 264 analyzed in conjunction, the average values of mesowear for this stage is 0.65 for bovids and
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27 265 0.61 for cervids.

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29 266 Species from the second zone of the Ventian (zone M2) also show a strong asymmetrical
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31 267 pattern and diet fluctuation (Table 1). Almost all species from Las Casiones and El Arquillo
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33 268 have about 50% sharp and 50% rounded apices and high relief, and scores ranging from 0.47 to
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35 269 0.63 (similar to several extant mixed feeders). *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* from Las Casiones
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37 270 differs instead from these in having a higher proportion of sharp cusps and a lower score of 0.31
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39 271 (such as some leaf-eaters). All the species from Milagros have teeth with stronger rounding and
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41 272 high relief, and scores between 0.69 and 0.79, which are indicative of intermediate levels of
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43 273 abrasion and diets similar to those of extant mixed feeders. *Pliocervus turolensis* from Milagros
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45 274 is the only species in this stage with the presence of blunt cusps and low occlusal relief (Table
46
47 275 1), which is indicative of a more abrasive diet. On average, MN13 (zone M2) bovids have
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49 276 scores of 0.60, whereas cervids exhibit a very slightly lower score of 0.58. There are microwear
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51 277 data for some species of this last stage (Table 2), which vary from moderately high (*Pliocervus*
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53 278 aff. *matheroni* from Las Casiones *Pliocervus turolensis* from El Arquillo) and intensive
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55 279 (*Pliocervus turolensis* from Las Casiones and *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* from El Arquillo)

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3 280 scratching and intermediate pitting incidences (for all species analysed), similar to those of the
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5 281 extant seasonal mixed feeders. This is in full agreement with data from mesowear.

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9 283 *Multivariate analyses and dietary assignment of the species*

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13 285 An explorative cluster analysis yielded two major clusters (Fig. 2A) clearly separating
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15 286 browsers (cluster A) from mixed feeders and grazers (cluster B). Among fossils, MN10 (zone
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17 287 J3) and MN11 (zone K) species cluster in B with extant species known to be mixed feeders (in
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19 288 subcluster B1). *Boselaphini* indet. 1 (Puente Minero) is in turn included in subcluster B2,
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21 289 together with the remaining extant mixed feeders and browse-dominated mixed feeders. Most of
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23 290 the MN12 (zone L) species clump also together with extant mixed feeders in subcluster B2,
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25 291 whereas a few (*Boselaphini* indet. 3 and *Hispanodorcas* sp. from Rambla de Río Seco E, and
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27 292 *Gazella deperdita* from Concud) are grouped with extant browsers in cluster A. A considerable
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29 293 heterogeneity in mesowear among MN13 (zone M1 and M2) populations is observed, implying
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31 294 the emplacement of species in all the diagram (cluster A and B). Overall, the analyses indicate a
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33 295 variable (mixed) diet for most of the fossil ruminants, with the exception of *Boselaphini* indet. 3
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35 296 and *Hispanodorcas* sp. from Rambla de Río Seco E, and *Gazella deperdita* from Concud
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37 297 (MN12); *Tragoportax* sp. and *Pliocervus* cf. *turoloensis* from Rambla de Río Seco K (MN13,
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39 298 zone M1), and *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* from Las Casiones (MN13, zone M2) which show
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41 299 greater affinities with extant browsers; and *Tragoportax gaudry* and cf. *Pliocervus* aff.
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43 300 *matheroni* (Valdecebro 3) (MN13, zone M1) which are more similar to grass-dominated mixed
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45 301 feeders.

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47 302 The discriminant Canonical Variate Analysis (CVA) (Fig. 2B, C) provides a satisfactory
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49 303 dietary discrimination, with 77.8% of extant taxa correctly classified by dietary categories
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51 304 according to a conservative classification (Fig. 2B). MN10 and MN11 (zones J3-K) species
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53 305 were classified as mixed feeders (Fig. 2B), while MN12 (zone L) ecosystems seem to have
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55 306 supported browsers (*Gazella deperdita* from Concud, and *Hispanodorcas* sp. and *Boselaphini*
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57 307 indet. 3 from Rambla de Río Seco E) and mixed feeders (all the remaining). MN13 species are

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3 308 more heterogeneous from a palaeodietary point of view, especially those of zone M1, such as
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5 309 *Tragoptax* sp. and *Pliocervus* cf. *turolensis* (Rambla de Río Seco K) that are considered as
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7 310 browsers. The Ventian (zone M2) populations were mostly classified as mixed feeders (Fig.
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9 311 2B), and only *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* (Las Casiones) was classified as a browser. CVA
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11 312 results based on a radical dietary classification (73.3% of extant taxa correctly classified) (Fig.
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13 313 2C) differ from those of the conservative for only three species: *Tragoptax gaudry* (RO2) and
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15 314 cf. *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* (Valdecebro 3) moved from the mixed feeder class toward the
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17 315 grazer one, whereas *Pliocervus* cf. *turolensis* (Valdecebro 3) moved from mixed feeder toward
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19 316 browser (Fig. 2C). This would imply that the two former exhibited a tendency towards grazing
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21 317 despite being mixed feeders (i.e., grass-dominated mixed feeders), while the latter was a mixed
22
23 318 feeder more inclined to browsing (browse-dominated mixed feeder). The CVA for microwear
24
25 319 (Table 2) confirms that the investigated variables provide a satisfactory dietary discrimination,
26
27 320 with 82.1% of extant taxa correctly classified, and shows very few changes in feeding style
28
29 321 according to tooth position. When considering the combination of upper and lower molars
30
31 322 (Table 2A), which allows for the largest sample size, the analysis indicates a seasonal mixed
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33 323 feeding for most of the fossil species, with the exception of *Lucentia* aff. *piemensis* and
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35 324 *Boselaphini* indet. 1 from Puente Minero, for which the analysis shows a frugivorous
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37 325 component.

326 327 **DISCUSSION**

328
329 *Palaeodiet and palaeoecology of late Miocene ruminants from the Alfambra-Teruel Basin*

330
331 Regarding cervids, species of *Lucentia* (MN11, zone K) and *Turiacemas* (MN12, zone L) are
332 here considered as mixed feeders, and display different wear patterns according to the site,
333 probably because of local differences in the abrasiveness of the resources. Discrepancies in
334 microwear and mesowear for *Lucentia* are interpreted as an indication of seasonal resource
335 differentiation, thereby corroborating that it was probably a mixed feeder including occasional

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3 336 browsing. This is in full agreement with dental wear inferences for *Lucentia* aff. *pierensis* from
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5 337 Rudabánya (Hungary) (Merceron *et al.* 2007). Recent isotopic data (Domingo *et al.* 2013) do
6
7 338 not support our view that *Turiacemas concudensis* from Concud engaged in both grazing and
8
9 339 browsing, as these authors suggested a diet based exclusively on browse for *Turiacemas*
10
11 340 *concudensis* according to low $d^{13}C$ values. This apparent incongruity can be due to the fact that
12
13 341 dental wear and stable isotopic signals provide dietary information at a different temporal scale,
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15 342 with tooth mesowear and microwear corresponding to longer (months/years) and shorter
16
17 343 (hours/days) scales, respectively, than isotopes. Also, the temporal scale of this latter approach
18
19 344 strongly depends on the sampling protocol for analysis (Hoppe *et al.* 2004). Apart from the
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21 345 species of Concud, our sample comprises also dental wear data for *Turiacemas* aff. *concudensis*
22
23 346 from Los Mansuetos, which provides further evidence for considering *Turiacemas* as a mixed
24
25 347 feeder. All the remaining (MN13) cervids belong to *Pliocervus*, and our analyses mostly reveal
26
27 348 mixed or browsing habits for both *Pliocervus turolensis* and *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* in the
28
29 349 different localities. There are, however, some intraspecific dietary differences that seem to be
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31 350 related to particular intervals, with a general trend of *Pliocervus* species exhibiting more
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33 351 opportunistic behaviours in the middle Ventian (MN13, zone M2) (with the exception of the
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35 352 browser *Pliocervus matheroni* from Las Casiones) and a narrow range of foods in the early
36
37 353 Ventian (zone M1).

38
39 354 In the case of the bovids, the boselaphine *Tragoportax* (with long limbs and postcranial
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41 355 anatomy suggesting cursorial adaptations and preference for open habitats; Köhler 1993) is
42
43 356 regarded as a mixed feeder, more engaged in grazing in some of the sites (for instance in La
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45 357 Roma 2, MN10). This is in agreement with tooth wear (Solounias & Hayek 1993; Merceron *et*
46
47 358 *al.* 2005, 2006) and isotopic (Zazzo *et al.* 2002; Domingo *et al.* 2013; Merceron *et al.* 2013)
48
49 359 data for *Tragoportax* species from the sites here considered and other comparable—similarly
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51 360 aged—Eurasian (Greece, Afghanistan, Bulgaria and Hungary) localities. It is important to
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53 361 stress, however, that *Tragoportax* could have been a possible browse-eater (either a browser or a
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55 362 browse-dominated mixed feeder) in the MN13 locality of Rambla de Río Seco K, as indicated
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57 363 by the predominance of cusp sharpness, high occlusal relief and low mesowear score. The

1
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3 364 remaining boselaphines are all mixed feeders, with the exception of species from Rambla de Río
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5 365 Seco E which has a significant browse component, although this conclusion must be tempered
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7 366 by a small sample. The Antilopinae *Hispanodorcas* had strong affinities with extant mixed
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9 367 feeders and browsers, which fits well with isotope data (Domingo *et al.* 2013) for the Spanish
10
11 368 *Hispanodorcas torrubiae* and microwear (Merceron *et al.* 2005) for the late Turolian
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13 369 *Hispanodorcas orientalis* from Greece. We provide for the first time data for the late Vallesian
14
15 370 Caprinae *Aragoral*, with a mesowear similar to that of a mixed feeder. Dental microwear
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17 371 confirms some seasonal variation in its foraging, as some specimens of the sample fed on grasses
18
19 372 (and related plants) prior to death while some others browsed. The common eland *Taurotragus*
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21 373 *oryx* might be a good dietary analogue of *Aragoral mudejar*, as shown by their almost identical
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23 374 scratching (898 and 870 scratches/mm², respectively) and pitting (619 and 591 pits/mm²)
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25 375 densities. Finally, mesowear suggests *Gazella* as a browser, and the high pit densities
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27 376 corroborate, at least, a strong browsing behaviour for this bovid. This is, however, in
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29 377 contradiction to studies that classify *Gazella deperdita* from Greece (Merceron *et al.* 2005) and
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31 378 *Gazella* sp. from Bulgaria (Merceron *et al.* 2006) as mixed feeders, but agrees instead in
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33 379 considering *Gazella vanhoepeni* as a browser (Sponheimer *et al.* 1999).

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35 380

36 381 *Late Miocene climatic and environmental evolution*

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39
40 383 It is possible to draw a more detailed scenario concerning the local response of environments
41
42 384 from the Alfambra-Teruel Basin to shifts in global climate when tooth wear patterns are traced
43
44 385 through time (Fig. 3A, B and Table 32).

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48 387 *Late Vallesian-early Turolian (MN10-MN11, local zones J3-K, ca. 9.0-7.7 Ma)*. A warm and
49
50 388 wet climate and warm-temperate forests have been inferred (Böhme *et al.* 2008; Pound *et al.*
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52 389 2011) for Europe during the Tortonian (11.61–7.25 Ma), with the Iberian Peninsula having
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54 390 instead drier, more open-adapted vegetation and a much more fragmentary biome pattern that
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56 391 could have favoured temperate sclerophyll woodlands and shrublands (Pound *et al.* 2011). Also,

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3 392 precipitation estimations based on rodent associations support a clear differentiation in humidity
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5 393 between North-East Spain (the Vallés-Penedés Basin) and central Spain (Calatayud-Teruel
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7 394 basins) (van Dam 2006; Maridet *et al.* 2013). The ruminant community here studied also
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9 395 reflects these environmental differences. Vallesian bovids—and most notably cervids—are very
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11 396 poorly documented in the inner basins of the Iberian Range, which is especially remarkable if
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13 397 compared with previous and later epochs. This supports the fact that the Vallesian Crisis
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15 398 affected more drastically those ruminants living in dryer landscapes. Muntjak-like deer were
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17 399 very rare elements in central Spain and there are no dental remains for these taxa. This,
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19 400 however, contrasts strongly with their abundance in the Vallés-Penedés and in central European
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21 401 basins. There are only two middle-large sized ruminants recorded in the late Vallesian (MN10)
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23 402 of central Spain. Thus, no dietary data based on the dental wear of the species are available for
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25 403 MN9 localities and those belonging to MN10 are still very scarce. Both the scarcity of cervids
26
27 404 and our new dietary data for late Vallesian (MN10) bovids indicate open habitats and dry
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29 405 climates (and open-habitat adapted vegetation as well) in the Teruel region after the Vallesian
30
31 406 Crisis. This is in accordance with small mammal (van Dam 2006) and isotope (Domingo *et al.*
32
33 407 2013) data suggesting La Roma 2 as a locality of pronounced aridity (mean annual precipitation
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35 408 [MAP] values ~314/200 mm/yr and mean annual temperature [MAT] of 26.2+5.4°C) which
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37 409 contrasts, however, with wetter environments (MAP 507 mm/yr) inferred from the herpetofauna
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39 410 of La Roma 2 (Böhme *et al.* 2008). Such a discrepancy may be due to either a more sensitive
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41 411 signal of the herpetofauna to detect local biotopes or because they appear to detect changes in
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43 412 time sooner than other groups of animals. Further evidence from pollen and spores found in
44
45 413 hyaena coprolites from La Roma 2 reveals a mixture of habitats in the surroundings of this
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47 414 locality, with relatively dense woodlands, less canopy cover areas (and lack of shrub taxa) and
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49 415 the presence of herbaceous plants developed under a temperate climate (Pesquero *et al.* 2011),
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51 416 which is in accordance with our finding of a somewhat dry climate and open woodland
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53 417 landscapes for the end of the Vallesian.

54 418 On the other hand, it is important to note the finding of a subtle (but clearly perceptible)
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56 419 decrease in the local abrasiveness of the foods and a greater dietary homogeneity in the early

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3 420 Turolian (MN11) (Fig. 3A, B). This was probably triggered by a period of relatively higher
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5 421 precipitation that favoured the existence of more humid conditions not only in central Spain, but
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7 422 also in southwestern Europe, as detected by Eronen *et al.* (2010b). Such a development of
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9 423 wetter environments in Teruel may have allowed a new group of cervids (i.e., the two-tined
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11 424 *Lucentia*, the first one bearing monopodial— a beam with offshoots of tines—antlers) to
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13 425 colonise the basin. Although dental remains of *Lucentia* aff. *pierensis* from Puente Minero are
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15 426 scarce, they seem to indicate a seasonal variation in food intake including occasional browsing,
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17 427 which fits well with a denser, wetter habitat.

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21 429 *Late Turolian (MN12, local zone L, ca. 7.7-7.0 Ma)*. Ruminants witnessed a complete renewal
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23 430 at the beginning of this interval. Although it is relatively abundant, there is only one (three-
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25 431 tined) deer species at this time, which contrasts with a burst of diversity in the bovids, with (at
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27 432 least) five different species being recorded in the basin: the boselophine *Tragoportax gaudryi*,
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29 433 two small-sized antilopines and two hippotragines. An increase in the diversity of available
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31 434 resources and the subsequent divergence in dietary traits (Fig. 3A, B) may help explain such a
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33 435 phenotypic diversity. Given that all the new bovids are mesodont and hypsodont forms, the
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35 436 development of more open habitats would be expected (Köhler 1993). However, our data reveal
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37 437 a clear dominance of the browsing niche, mainly as a consequence of the wear patterns of the
38
39 438 new small-sized *Gazella* and *Hispanodorcas* (Fig. 3A, B). This contrasts with the lack of small-
40
41 439 sized species and the more abrasive diets recorded in the late Vallesian (MN10).

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43 440 Notably, a progressive transition towards more humid conditions at the end of the Turolian
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45 441 (MN12, zone L) can be inferred from decreases in mesowear scores (Fig. 3A, B). Thus, a
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47 442 number of species (*Gazella deperdita*, *Hispanodorcas* sp. and a boselaphine bovid) primarily
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49 443 browsed on monocotyledon foods, probably in considerably wet and closed areas in sites like
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51 444 Concud and Rambla de Río Seco E (Fig. 3A, B). Among extant ungulates, there are only
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53 445 browser species with mesowear scores lower than 0.20, which indicates a diet based on leaves
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55 446 and twigs for these late Turolian species. If our data (Fig. 3) are compared with the isotope
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57 447 curve constructed by Ezquerro *et al.* (2014) using the stable isotope composition of lacustrine

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3 448 carbonates in the area, we observe oxygen ($d^{18}O$) values decreasing at ca. 7.0 Ma. This confirms
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5 449 that the humidity increase deduced for the late Turolian (~ 7.0 Ma, MN12) was the cause of the
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7 450 lacustrine expansion at the end of their so-called "lacustrine stage 2". Similarly, previous studies
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9 451 of sedimentary sequences and facies in the study area have proposed that carbonate lacustrine
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11 452 deposits were deposited at the top of the stratigraphic "Unit II" (see Alsonso-Zarza & Calvo,
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13 453 2000; Alsonso-Zarza *et al.* 2012), in a palustrine or a more permanent (but shallow) lacustrine
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15 454 setting, which provides evidence of a peak indicative of more humid and cooler climatic
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17 455 conditions ca. 7.0 Ma. Furthermore, the change to more humid conditions here detected through
18
19 456 the dental wear of ruminants perfectly matches with the micromammalian community—also
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21 457 easily affected by climate instability—, as the rich talpid assemblage developed in Concud is a
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23 458 strong indication of increased levels of humidity (Rümke 1974). Despite such a dietary
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25 459 specialisation in most of the ruminants, an exclusive dominance of dense forests can be
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27 460 discarded, as denoted by the presence of several mixed feeders (also depending on some grasses
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29 461 and abrasives). This is supported by the fact that some specimens of *Tragoportax gaudry* have a
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31 462 high pitting incidence, several of which are large, which indicates the presence of hard particles
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33 463 in the local habitats. Nonetheless, the absence of strict grazing indicates undoubtedly that
34
35 464 grasslands were still not sufficiently widespread. This is paramount, as our dietary data discard
36
37 465 a complete opening of the Mediterranean habitats throughout the Turolian and the formation of
38
39 466 a new component in the structure of the landscape cover—the steppe zone—with extensive
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41 467 grass (and steppe-like) vegetation, or at least a much less important opening than other studies
42
43 468 have suggested before. Instead, we rather suggest the presence of mixed landscapes with the
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45 469 presence of both closed and open landscapes ca. 7.0 Ma. Accordingly, our data contradict earlier
46
47 470 assumptions and clearly provide evidence that the common view of the steppe as the landscape
48
49 471 dominant in the late Miocene is a major misconception. It is also worth mentioning that such a
50
51 472 climatic trend was apparently synchronic in both deer and bovids. Our data appear largely
52
53 473 consistent with the palaeoclimatic evidence derived from plant evidence (Jiménez-Moreno *et al.*
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55 474 2010) from NE Spain. Moreover, for most of the Tortonian (ca. 11.6-7.2 Ma), the mean annual
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57 475 precipitation values are generally estimated to be higher than present-day values (Böhme *et al.*

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3 476 2008), which is also consistent with the humidity gradient here detected at the end of the
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5 477 Turolian.
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9 479 *Early Ventian (MN13, local zones M1 and M2, from 7.0 Ma)*. A general, prominent shift
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11 480 towards more dietary heterogeneity and ecological diversification (and a return to more arid and
12
13 481 warmer conditions) is observed during the early Ventian (~ 6.8 Ma), as showed by the disparity
14
15 482 (Fig. 3A, B) and general increase of mesowear values. These differences reveal the existence of
16
17 483 a differential resource utilization and niche segregation in the species, with the presence of
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19 484 mixed feeders, taxa showing wholly browse lifestyles, and ruminants engaged in grazing. The
20
21 485 new environmental conditions may have facilitated the deposit and the adhesion to food items
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23 486 of grit and dust (Kaiser & Rössner 2007), and hence the higher levels of abrasion found in the
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25 487 teeth of *Tragoportax gaudry* and *Pliocervus* aff. *matheroni* in Valdecebro 3 (Fig. 3B). Samples
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27 488 of the last time interval (MN13, zone M2) are much more abundant than those of zone M1, and
28
29 489 support the hypothesis of a transition from a long humid period (with a peak of humidity at ~7.0
30
31 490 Ma) to a more variable climate. The development of a marked seasonality of precipitation
32
33 491 would result in more open and dry environments locally evolved, and the subsequent response
34
35 492 of a number of species to increase the amount of grass in diets, leaving them well suited to cope
36
37 493 with the new environmental circumstances. Similarly, any short interval of increased humidity
38
39 494 would have triggered the development of somewhat more bushy environments and arboreal
40
41 495 vegetation, which would explain the existence of species committed to browsing (as *Pliocervus*
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43 496 aff. *matheroni*, among others, in Las Casiones) and the first appearance of hippopotamuses in
44
45 497 the Mediterranean (Morales *et al.* 2013). Because strong seasonality and/or global aridity seem
46
47 498 to be a restricting factor for the development of fully wooded and forested habitats, we can
48
49 499 discard an exclusive dominance of forested ecosystems in the basin during this time, but also
50
51 500 (again) an excessive development of open landscapes. Overall, our results agree very well with
52
53 501 hypsodonty-based palaeoprecipitation maps and dietary structure of the mammalian plant-eater
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55 502 community (Fortelius *et al.* 2006) for this epoch. Palaeobotanic proxies (Böhme *et al.* 2017)
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57 503 have also suggested that water-stress levels and increased aridification occurred in the

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3 504 Mediterranean on a global scale at the beginning of the Messinian (i.e., our early Ventian).
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5 505 These changes were likely to have led to the spread of new mammalian taxa—including the
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7 506 hominid *Graecopithecus*—into Europe. Thus, the open, C4 grass-dominated habitats inferred
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9 507 after the Tortonian in the Mediterranean (Böhme *et al.* 2017) coincide with the intensification of
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11 508 the aridity that we detect locally in the Teruel-Alfambra Basin in MN13 (Fig. 3B) and the more
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13 509 open, arid environments evolved in this area. Our local estimations can be also correlated to the
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15 510 increasing aridity trend in the Mediterranean recently inferred through the early Messinian
16
17 511 diatomaceous deposition (Pellegrino *et al.* 2018). Furthermore, and although there are no pollen
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19 512 data available for the Alfambra-Teruel Basin during this interval (only for southern and
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21 513 northeastern regions of the Iberian Peninsula), vegetation models for the Mediterranean
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23 514 according to pollen records (Favre *et al.* 2007) show a zonal distribution along the Iberian
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25 515 Peninsula (Favre *et al.* 2007; Jiménez-Moreno *et al.* 2010) with a clear limit (xerophytic
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27 516 vegetation/subtropical forests) near the Alfambra-Teruel Basin. The presence of such limit may
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29 517 attest that particular environmental conditions— that general climate models fail to establish—
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31 518 occurred for this intra-mountainous basin during the late Miocene.

32 519

34 520 *Environmental synthesis and correlation with late Miocene major faunal events*

36 521

38 522 Overall, the high record of mixed feeders (some of them—as *Tragoportax* in La Roma 2—
39 523 committed to grazing) and the lack of browsers in the Vallesian (MN10) and early Turolian
40 524 (MN11) suggest open woodlands including closed areas and more open patches for this interval,
41 525 with a significant development of grass and abrasives. Then, we interpret the changes in tooth
42 526 wear together with other proxies as a shift towards more humid/cool environmental conditions
43 527 which gradually intensified and reached a peak of humidity at the end of the Turolian (MN12,
44 528 ~7.0 Ma). Certainly, such a climate would have favoured mixed landscapes with an important
45 529 canopy coverage and well developed arboreal and soft vegetation, and limited an excessive
46 530 development of grasses and some other plants typical of grasslands and savannas. Our data
47 531 indicate that the early Ventian (MN13, zones M1 and M2, ca. 7.0-6.0 Ma) was in general

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3 532 characterised by drier and warmer conditions and more seasonal landscapes. This can be
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5 533 understood in an scenario with pronounced oscillation in climate as a result of a strong
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7 534 seasonality (see DeMiguel *et al.* 2010). A greater dietary breadth and more open adapted species
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9 535 (also engaged in grazing) suggest that a summer-dry and winter-wet pattern may have appeared
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11 536 intermittently in the basin and affected the stability of the ecosystems. Finally, the climate
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13 537 seems to have evolved towards warmer and drier, preceding the conditions that ultimately led to
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15 538 the first desiccation phase of the Salinity Crisis in the Mediterranean.

16
17 539 From a wider perspective, what is important here is that our data together with results from
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19 540 previous authors (Rümke 1974; van Dam 1997; Alonso-Zarza & Calvo 2000; Böhme *et al.*
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21 541 2008, 2011; Alonso-Zarza *et al.* 2012; Ezquerro *et al.* 2014) using different approaches
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23 542 (micromammal communities, tectono-sedimentary analyses, stratigraphical evolution and
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25 543 isotopic analysis of carbonates, etc.) indicate that this phase of increased humidity and humid-
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27 544 adapted vegetation was coeval with a moment of global drying and cooling. Thus, the
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29 545 diversification of aridity-adapted cacti and succulent plants between 10.0-5.0 Ma (Arakaki *et al.*
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31 546 2011); the restriction of the Parathetys and the establishment of the Sahara Desert at ca. 7 Ma
32
33 547 (Zhang *et al.* 2014); or the expansion of C⁴ grasslands at the expense of C³-dominated
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35 548 ecosystems dating to 8-6 Myr ago (Cerling *et al.* 1997) are, among others, some relevant facts
36
37 549 that inform about the magnitude and wide range of this global event.

38
39 550 Regarding major faunal events, four prominent turnover pulses associated with the Alpine
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41 551 Neogene tectogenic phases (Pickford & Morales 1994) are recognised in Southwestern Europe
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43 552 during the last 22.5 Myr, among which two of them occurred during the late Miocene, our focus
44
45 553 here. The first was the so-called Vallesian Crisis (early/late Vallesian), firstly recognised as a
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47 554 local episode in the Catalan coastal basins (Casanovas-Vilar *et al.* 2014). The record of the
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49 555 Alfambra-Teruel Basin shows a number of extinctions that occurred during the late Vallesian
50
51 556 (MN10) but over a longer time interval (~9.5 to 9.1 Ma) to that of the Vallès-Penedès Basin
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53 557 (van Dam 1997). Although the causes of the Vallesian Crisis are still unclear, several recent
54
55 558 works have found that the event coincides with 1) a positive trend in benthic foraminifera $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
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57 559 values that reflects global cooling conditions (Westerhold *et al.* 2005); 2) an increase of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$

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3 560 values of Spanish herbivorous mammals between MN9 and MN10 that relates to a local change
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5 561 towards drier conditions (Domingo *et al.* 2013); and 3) a decrease in precipitation at 9.7–9.6 Ma
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7 562 using the ecophysiological structure of late Miocene Spanish herpetofaunas (Böhme *et al.*
8
9 563 2011). According to our results, however, the feeding ecology of the herbivores suggests more
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11 564 humid conditions than expected and a persistence of forested areas during the late Vallesian
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13 565 (~9.1 Ma) (for example in La Roma 2), which is entirely in agreement with several works that
14
15 566 show no drastic changes in regional vegetation or climatic conditions in Spain during the
16
17 567 Vallesian (Agustí *et al.* 2003). The second faunal event correlates with the last phase of the
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19 568 Alpine orogeny (Rhodanian tectogenic phase) (Fig. 3) that caused the close of the occidental
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21 569 Mediterranean, and matches the last Turolian faunas and the beginning of the Ventian (ca. 7.8-6
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23 570 Ma) and continues with the Messinian Salinity Crisis (5.96-5.33 Ma). Iberian mammals of this
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25 571 time reflect the general trend in climate of the last part of the Miocene (relatively high
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27 572 temperatures and humidity; van Dam 2006), which led to the development of Asian-influenced
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29 573 associations (Morales *et al.* 2013). Northeast migrations were also largely favored by these
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31 574 conditions. The interchange was initially moderate during the first Ventian subzones (M1 and
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33 575 M2), though coincided with an increase in humidity (in subzone M2) that allowed the dispersal
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35 576 of hippopotamuses. This interchange acquired a massive character during the M3 and witnessed
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37 577 the arrival of Asian and North American mammals, such as camels, new carnivores
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39 578 (*Agriotherium*, *Eucyon* and *Lutra*), and modern ruminants (the oldest Western Europe Bovini
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41 579 *Parabos*). The mammals of this period are, therefore, very heterogeneous in both composition
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43 580 (Morales *et al.* 2013) and ecological requirements, which perfectly fits with the pronounced
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45 581 oscillations in climate and the strong local environmental shifts that we detect for this time.

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48 583 **CONCLUSIONS**

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52 585 New information on the diet (obtained through tooth-wear patterns) and ecology of large
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54 586 mammals helps trace the environmental evolution of the Teruel-Alfambra Basin during the late
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56 587 Miocene in more detail, especially concerning changes in local climate and habitat conditions.

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3 588 Regarding the the Vallesian (MN10, zone J3) and early Turolian (MN11, zone K), the absence
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5 589 of deer, the lack of strict browsing bovids and an abundance of opportunistic bovids (some
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7 590 engaged in grazing) indicate a relatively dry climate and open woodland landscapes with open-
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9 591 habitat adapted grasses. This suggests that this event did affect more drastically ruminants living
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11 592 in dry areas. From 8.5 Ma onwards, our data indicate a subtle but perceptible period of
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13 593 relatively higher precipitation that favoured the existence of denser, wetter environments in
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15 594 Teruel, which probably allowed a new group of monopodial-antlered deer to colonise the basin.
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17 595 We find that such a shift did reach a peak indicative of humid/cool conditions at the end of the
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19 596 Turolian (MN12, zone L, ~7.0 Ma), which led species to intensive browsing in environments
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21 597 with an important canopy coverage and arboreal vegetation. Our new data exclude, therefore,
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23 598 the hypothesis that a complete opening of the Mediterranean habitats occurred throughout the
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25 599 Turolian, and contradict earlier works and the widespread view of the steppe as the landscape
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27 600 dominant in the late Miocene. Lastly, there was a prominent shift towards strong dietary
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29 601 fluctuation from the early Ventian onwards (MN13, zone M1), with most of the species being
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31 602 mixed feeders, some taxa showing wholly browsing lifestyles, and others being engaged in
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33 603 grazing. We find that rapidly changing ecosystems evolved locally for this period, with the
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35 604 alternation of open/dry habitats and more bushy/arboreal environments.

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37 605 Because all this occurred within a global drying trend in Europe, our data support the view
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39 606 that the greatest changes in climate may have an opposite impact at regional and local scales,
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41 607 which is critically important for understanding the expected consequences of global warming.
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43 608 That is, under arid/warm global conditions, a more humid/cool climate in some regions may
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45 609 represent a possible scenario for future global climate change. Accordingly, we need to be
46
47 610 aware of the uncertainties associated with climate so that we can weigh them in formulation of
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49 611 strategies to cope with the risks of climate change.

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42 **Figure legends**

43
44 **FIG. 1.** Schematic geological maps. A, location of the studied region within the Iberian
45 Peninsula. B, detailed map showing the Alfambra-Teruel Graben (central Spain) that has
46 delivered dental remains studied in this paper (~~modified from Álvarez-Sierra *et al.* 2003~~).
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51 **FIG. 2.** Results of the Cluster analysis and the CVA based on dental wear features. A,
52 Hierarchical cluster based on the percentage of high occlusal relief, round cusps and blunt
53 cusps. B, CVA based on a conservative dietary classification. C, CVA based on a radical
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3 913 classification. The first dietary assignment of the species corresponds to that of the conservative
4 914 classification, and the second informs about a possible foraging specialisation (or dietary
5 915 tendency) in generalist species. The ellipses showing the variability of extant dietary categories
6 916 (browsers, mixed feeders and grazers) are depicted in black. Large crosses denote group
7 917 centroids. Data of extant species from Fortelius & Solounias (2000). Colored symbols denote
8 918 the time interval to which each species belong, black symbols representing extant taxa.
9
10 919 Abbreviations of fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones (KS); Valdecebro
11 920 3 (VDC3); Rambla de Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE); Los Mansuetos
12 921 (LM); Concud (CD); Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2). COLOUR.

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14 922
15 923 **FIG. 3.** The late Miocene scenario. A, evolutionary trend of mesowear values of species from
16 924 the Teruel-Alfambra region traced according to chronological sequence of the sites and
17 925 geological and biotic events. ~~Cervids in red colour and bovids in blue.~~ B, simplified tendency of
18 926 the tooth wear calculated from average values of the late Miocene localities (see Table [32](#) for
19 927 further information). Black arrows indicate periods of strong fluctuation in humidity and
20 928 temperature . Abbreviations of fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones
21 929 (KS); Valdecebro 3 (VDC3); Rambla de Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE);
22 930 Los Mansuetos (LM); Concud (CD); Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2). ~~COLOUR.~~
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Schematic geological maps. A, location of the studied region within the Iberian Peninsula. B, detailed map showing the Alfambra-Teruel Graben (central Spain) that has delivered dental remains studied in this paper.

71x46mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Results of the Cluster analysis and the CVA based on dental wear features. A, Hierarchical cluster based on the percentage of high occlusal relief, round cusps and blunt cusps. B, CVA based on a conservative dietary classification. C, CVA based on a radical classification. The first dietary assignment of the species corresponds to that of the conservative classification, and the second informs about a possible foraging specialisation (or dietary tendency) in generalist species. The ellipses showing the variability of extant dietary categories (browsers, mixed feeders and grazers) are depicted in black. Large crosses denote group centroids. Data of extant species from Fortelius & Solounias (2000). Colored symbols denote the time interval to which each species belong, black symbols representing extant taxa. Abbreviations of fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones (KS); Valdecebro 3 (VDC3); Rambla de Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE); Los Mansuetos (LM); Conclud (CD); Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2). COLOUR.

239x346mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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The late Miocene scenario. A, evolutionary trend of mesowear values of species from the Teruel-Alfambra region traced according to chronological sequence of the sites and geological and biotic events. B, simplified tendency of the tooth wear calculated from average values of the late Miocene localities (see Table 3 for further information). Black arrows indicate periods of strong fluctuation in humidity and temperature. Abbreviations of fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones (KS); Valdecebro 3 (VDC3); Rambla de Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE); Los Mansuetos (LM); Conclud (CD); Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2).

93x52mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Table 1. Species studied and summary of dental mesowear ~~and microwear~~ results.

MN	Species	GR	Site	Zone	Ma	N	pH	pL	pS	pR	pB	MS	N	S[SD]	P[SD]	
MN13	<i>Pliocervus turolensis</i>	C	AQ	M2	6.33	12	100	0.0	36.3	63.7	0.0	0.63	7	788[138]	368[116]	
	<i>Pliocervus aff. matheroni</i>	C	AQ	M2	6.33	20	100	0.0	44.7	55.3	0.0	0.55	7	1050[289]	479[98]	
	<i>Pliocervus turolensis</i>	C	ML	M2	6.33	18	88.9	11.1	38.2	53.0	8.8	0.79	-	-	-	
	<i>Pliocervus aff. matheroni</i>	C	ML	M2	6.33	7	100	0.0	30.8	69.2	0.0	0.69	-	-	-	
	<i>Tragoptax sp.</i>	B	ML	M2	6.33	53	100	0.0	27.8	72.2	0.0	0.72	-	-	-	
	<i>Pliocervus turolensis</i>	C	KS	M2	6.33	9	100	0.0	52.9	47.1	0.0	0.47	4	916[262]	561[265]	
	<i>Pliocervus aff. matheroni</i>	C	KS	M2	6.33	60	100	0.0	68.9	31.1	0.0	0.31	9	751[301]	594[470]	
	<i>Tragoptax sp.</i>	B	KS	M2	6.33	39	92.3	7.7	53.8	46.2	0.0	0.55	-	-	-	
	<i>Boselaphini indet. 2</i>	B	KS	M2	6.33	15	100	0.0	48.0	52.0	0.0	0.52	-	-	-	
			C	MN13	M2		126	98.1	1.8	45.3	53.2	1.4	0.57			
		B	MN13	M2		107	97.4	2.6	43.2	56.8	0.0	0.60				
MN13	<i>Pliocervus cf. turolensis</i>	C	VDC3	M1	~6.9	1	100	0.0	50	50	0.0	0.50	-	-	-	
	<i>cf. Pliocervus aff. matheroni</i>	C	VDC3	M1	~6.9	5	80	20	28.6	42.8	28.6	1.28	-	-	-	
	<i>Tragoptax gaudryi</i>	B	VDC3	M1	~6.9	1	100	0.0	0	100	0.0	1.00	-	-	-	
	<i>Boselaphini indet. cf. Tragoptax</i>	B	VDC3	M1	~6.9	4	100	0.0	40	60.0	0.0	0.60	-	-	-	
	<i>Boselaphini indet. 4</i>	B	VDC3	M1	~6.9	3	100	0.0	20	80.0	0.0	0.80	-	-	-	
	<i>Pliocervus cf. turolensis</i>	C	RRSK	M1	~6.9	1	100	0.0	100	0.0	0.0	0.00	-	-	-	
	<i>cf. Pliocervus aff. matheroni</i>	C	RRSK	M1	~6.9	5	100	0.0	33.3	66.6	0.0	0.66	-	-	-	
	<i>Tragoptax sp.</i>	B	RRSK	M1	~6.9	5	100	0.0	80	20.0	0.0	0.20	-	-	-	
			C	MN13	M1		12	95	5.0	52.3	39.9	7.1	0.61			
			B	MN13	M1		13	100	0.0	35.0	65.0	0.0	0.65			
MN12	<i>Boselaphini indet. 3</i>	B	RRSE	L	~7.0	1	100	0.0	100	0.0	0.0	0.00	-	-	-	
	<i>Hispanodorcas sp.</i>	B	RRSE	L	~7.0	2	100	0.0	75.0	25.0	0.0	0.25	-	-	-	
	<i>Turiacemas aff. concudensis</i>	C	LM	L	7.1	4	100	0.0	33.3	66.6	0.0	0.66	-	-	-	
	<i>Hispanodorcas torrubiae</i>	B	LM	L	7.1	6	100	0.0	33.3	66.6	0.0	0.66	-	-	-	
	<i>Turiacemas concudensis</i>	C	CD	L	7.1	16	93.8	6.2	52.0	48.0	0.0	0.56	-	-	-	
	<i>Tragoptax gaudryi</i>	B	CD	L	7.1	29	100	0.0	41.7	58.3	0.0	0.58	6	1022[359]	570[175]	
	<i>Gazella deperdita</i>	B	CD	L	7.1	46	95.7	4.3	68.9	31.1	0.0	0.36	8	835[263]	643[149]	
			C	MN12	L		20	96.9	3.1	42.7	57.3	0.0	0.61			
			B	MN12	L		84	99.1	0.86	63.8	36.2	0.0	0.37			
	MN11	<i>Lucentia aff. pierensis</i>	C	PM	K	8.51	7	100	0.0	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.80	6	620[160]	275[63]
<i>Tragoptax gaudryi</i>		B	PM	K	8.51	59	93.2	6.8	30.1	69.9	0.0	0.76	7	1047[191]	463[175]	
<i>Boselaphini indet. 1</i>		B	PM	K	8.51	3	100	0.0	40.0	60.0	0.0	0.60	3	641[121]	244[97]	
		C	MN11	K		7	100	0.0	20.0	80.0	0.0	0.80				
		B	MN11	K		62	96.6	3.4	35.1	64.9	0.0	0.68				
MN10	<i>Aragoral mudejar</i>	B	RO2	J	9.1	22	100	0.0	24.2	75.8	0.0	0.75	7	870[119]	591[384]	
	<i>Tragoptax gaudryi</i>	B	RO2	J	9.1	30	93.3	6.7	17.3	80.8	1.9	0.90	6	719[159]	398[120]	
		B	MN10	J		52	96.7	3.3	20.8	78.3	0.9	0.82				

Abbreviations: Taxonomic group (GR); Cervidae (C); Bovidae (B); million years (Ma); number of specimens measured (N); percentage of specimens with high (pH) and low (pL) occlusal relief; percentage of specimens with sharp (pS), rounded (pR) and blunt (pB) cusps; and

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3 mesowear score (MS); ~~scratches/mm² (S); pits/mm² (P); and standard deviation (SD)~~. Fossil
4 sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones (KS); Valdecebro 3 (VDC3); Rambla de
5 Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE); Los Mansuetos (LM); Concud (CD);
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7 Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2). The average values for each taxonomic group in the
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9 time intervals are in black. Ages were assigned according to (1) van Dam *et al.* (2006) based on
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11 correlation to local magnetostratigraphically dated sections, cyclo and lithostratigraphic
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13 extrapolation, and biostratigraphic correlation; and (2) Domingo *et al.* (2014) based on a
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15 biochronological study of the Upper Neogene of the Iberian Peninsula using the maximum
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17 likelihood appearance event ordination method (Alroy 2000).
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Table 2. Summary of dental microwear results according to the combination of tooth type (A, upper + lower; B, only lower teeth; and C, only upper teeth) selected for study.

Species	Site	A			82.1% DIET	B			82.1% DIET	C			82.1% DIET
		upper + lower	N	S[SD]		P[SD]	only lower	N		S[SD]	P[SD]	only upper	
<i>Pliocervus turolensis</i>	AQ	7	788[138]	368[116]	SM	4	812[154]	330[67]	SM	3	756[136]	416[165]	SM
<i>Pliocervus</i> aff. <i>matheroni</i>	AQ	7	1050[289]	479[98]	SM	4	967[374]	457[105]	SM	3	1160[98]	506[102]	G
<i>Pliocervus turolensis</i>	KS	4	916[262]	561[265]	SM	3	901[319]	624[284]	SM	1	959	368	SM
<i>Pliocervus</i> aff. <i>matheroni</i>	KS	9	751[301]	594[470]	SM	4	912[84]	463[283]	SM	5	622[360]	699[407]	LB
<i>Tragoportax gaudryi</i>	CD	6	1022[359]	570[175]	SM	3	966[467]	621[229]	SM	3	1079[307]	517[128]	SM
<i>Gazella deperdita</i>	CD	8	835[263]	643[319]	SM	4	868[358]	740[417]	SM	4	802[173]	546[197]	SM
<i>Lucentia</i> aff. <i>piensis</i>	PM	6	620[160]	275[63]	FB	1	737	264	SM	5	596[167]	276[70]	FB
<i>Tragoportax gaudryi</i>	PM	7	1047[191]	463[175]	SM	1	932	360	SM	6	1066[202]	480[186]	SM
<i>Boselaphini</i> indet. 1	PM	3	641[121]	244[97]	FB	1	781	143	SM	2	570[3]	295[61]	FB
<i>Aragoral mudejar</i>	RO2	7	870[119]	591[384]	SM	2	781[116]	548[181]	SM	5	906[111]	608[460]	SM
<i>Tragoportax gaudryi</i>	RO2	6	719[159]	398[120]	SM	4	773[140]	548[181]	SM	2	609[181]	366[168]	FB

Abbreviations: Number of specimens measured (N); scratches/mm² (S); pits/mm² (P); standard

deviation (SD); seasonal mixed feeding (SM); fruit browsing (FB); grazing (G); and leaf

browsing (LB). Fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Las Casiones (KS); Conclud (CD); Puente

Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2). As it can be seen, there is a very high predictive power of the discriminant analysis. This means that among the 28 extant ungulates used to fit the model, 82.1% are correctly classified according to the microwear densities. This percentage is the same in the three analyses because it refers to the same extant baseline sample and variables and it does not affect to the fossil cases. Data for microwear are highly robust and offer very few changes in feeding style for the fossil cases (see DIET column) according to tooth type. As it can be seen, data for microwear are highly robust and offer very few changes in feeding style.

Most of these changes apply to those specimens with the lowest sample size, and the fact of grouping upper and lower teeth does not always inflate the guild of mixed feeder species, since there is a higher number of mixed feeders when considering only lower tooth positions.

Table 23. Mean, standard error and standard deviation of mesowear values.

	RO2	PM	CD	LM	RRSE	RRSK	VDC3	KS	ML	AQ
N	84	128	110	18	5	13	15	210	148	60
Mean	0,857	0,765	0,454	0,666	0,2	0,384	0,933	0,423	0,736	0,583
Std. error	0,056	0,048	0,055	0,114	0,2	0,140	0,248	0,037	0,046	0,064
SD	0,518	0,553	0,584	0,485	0,4	0,506	0,961	0,550	0,563	0,497

Abbreviations: Number of specimens (N); and standard deviation (SD). Fossil sites: El Arquillo (AQ); Milagros (ML); Las Casiones (KS); Valdecebro 3 (VDC3); Rambla de Río Seco K (RRSK); Rambla de Río Seco E (RRSE); Los Mansuetos (LM); Concud (CD); Puente Minero (PM); La Roma 2 (RO2).